

Conference Abstract

DNA barcode reference libraries: Achievements of the DNAqua-Net Working Group 1

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Abstract

The three main aims for the DNAqua-Net working group 1 (WG1) have been i) to identify gaps in the barcode reference libraries of European aquatic species, ii) to fill these gaps in collaboration with ongoing initiatives, and iii) to facilitate knowledge transfer and initiate work on barcode reference libraries in regions where such activity was low (Leese et al. 2016). WG1 currently has 129 members from 39 countries spanning four continents, with a majority of members from Europe.

In our presentation we show the achievements of WG1 during the lifetime of the DNAqua-Net COST action (CA15219; 2016-2021), and discuss some of the highlights obtained through collaborative work and joint dissemination. Specifically, we emphasize the outcomes presented in two peer-reviewed scientific publications that focus on standards for building DNA barcode reference libraries, and gaps in reference databases for European aquatic organisms currently used in national biomonitoring programs (Rimet et al. 2021, Weigand et al. 2019). However, major achievements were also obtained in four workshops (Braga, Pécs, Limassol & Bratislava) and through the activities of 16 short-term scientific missions (STSMs).

Keywords

DNAqua-Net, WG1, DNA barcode, reference libraries

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